

From Puranas to Politics : The Mythic Imagination in Kanthapura

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Abstract

Raja Rao has skillfully and intelligently drawn upon the diverse facets of Indian mythology, being fully aware of its wealth. His utilization of myth is discursive and digressional. In his renowned "Foreword" to *Kanthapura* (1938), Raja Rao asserts, "Episode follows episode, and when our thoughts stop, our breath stops, and we proceed to another thought. This was, and still is, the ordinary style of our storytelling. I have tried to follow it myself in this story."1 (6) the characters in his novels consistently exhibit archetypal patterns in their thoughts and reactions to life. He endeavors to portray the universality of human emotions by interlacing narratives with his work. His novels make extensive use of Indian mythology. He primarily employs three types of myths: (a) Puranic Myths (b) Localized Myths (c) Rites and Rituals

Keywords

Myth, Rituals, Purana, Gandhi, Ideology.

Introduction

In the works of Raja Rao puranic myths are characterized by the binary opposition of the good and the evil, as illustrated by the characters of Rama and Ravana- the fundamental myth that Raja Rao employs in *Kanthapura*. The Gandhian struggle against the cruel Britishers is described by the opposites of the good and the bad. *Kanthapura* is primarily a retelling of the localized myth, which Raja Rao refers to as *sthala-purana*² (5), which is the mythical history of a village located on the western coast of India. Localized myths have also been employed and Raja Rao has reconstructed history and presented it by mythologizing the historical characters and utilizing legendary stories of India.

In *The Serpant and the Rope* (1968) Raja Rao sees mythical connections in a wide range of human experiences and his magical perception takes on multifaceted shapes. It takes form of two-sided relationships Radha -Krishna, Satyavan-Savitri, and Tristan-Iseult mirrored in the relationship of Ramaswamy and Savithri. *The Cat and Shakespeare* (1965) also portrays the myth of the hunter and the bilva tree. Raja Rao's novel *Comrade Kirillov* (1976) is different from his other novels because it doesn't mythicise the story but *Comrade Kirillov's* search for self-realization is given mythical power by linking it to the story of *Kanthaka*, the horse that carried Siddhartha to his goal of self-realization.

Objective of study

The paper attempts to analyse extensive use of myth woven by Raja Rao in his novel *Kanthapura*. The narrative is interlaced with local stories of the deities, with myths from *Ramayana*, *Mahabharata*, and *Puranas* in a seamless manner. The objective of the study is to examine how mythic background has been used to instill in simple villagers a zest for freedom struggle. Indian imagination is especially amenable to religious anecdotes from religion. Religious activities are part and parcel of daily routine of common people. Miracles happen at the crossroads of the street. Gods walk at night and deities intervene in the life of people. Even the narrative of Gandhi's birth is interspersed with stories akin to birth of avatar. The paper explores how different kinds of myths have been used to create a dynamic political environment, where Moorthy becomes the representative of Gandhi and Gandhi becomes an incarnation of Shiva.

Review of Literature

The study of myth in Indian literature, particularly in the works of Raja Rao, has been richly explored from multiple perspectives. Scholars such as Rajesh K. Pallan, Meenakshi Mukherji and P.Lal have noted Rao's use of three distinct mythic forms, puranic myths, localized myths and rites/rituals which he interweaves to create a layered narrative. Critics have noted how Raja Rao's mythic technique elevates *Kanthapura* from a mere political chronicle to a mythological *Purana*. Akash Satpati in his research paper *Unique Blending of Myth and Reality in Raja Rao's Kanthapura: A Critical Study* analyzes important mythic characters and rituals. Parimal Kumar and Tapan Kumar Biswas have examined oral tradition and meaningfulness of incorporating myth in narrative.

Main Text

Raja Rao has used the many layers of Indian mythology in an ingenious manner, masked as structured warfare for India's liberation from British oppression and is illustrated in the altruistic narrative. The novel ostensibly focuses on political revival and is replete with myths that Raja Rao has adeptly integrated into his artistic tapestry. The regional legends of Goddess Kenchamma and her daughter Himavathy are intricately interwoven within it. The novel expresses the philosophy of selfless love and sacrifice found in the *Bhagavad Gita*. The Gandhian struggle for emancipation against the Red Man's merciless power is portrayed through the dichotomy of good and evil as exemplified by Rama and Ravana. *Kanthapura* is depicted as a literal *Kurukshetra*, with the Indian liberation movement likened to the epic conflict of the *Mahabharata*. Raja Rao has mythologized historical figures such as Gandhi to illustrate the conflict between the

righteous and the wicked, truth and falsehood, and love and hatred. The transition between civilizations has been depicted as an ongoing cycle of cyclical processes, utilizing the Indian concept of eternity and permanence. The novel alludes to mythical analogies through depiction of the rites and rituals that pervade it. The cultural experiences of the Puranic universe are amplified in the contemporary Indian realities of a small village's quest for independence. Raja Rao adeptly encapsulates "the whole ethos of Indian villagers"³(Raizada 197) through a multitude of narratives. His writing in the novel's "Foreword" illustrates the profound significance of myth "There is no Indian village in India, however mean, that has not a rich *sthala-Purana* or a legendary history of its own. Some god or god like-hero has passed by the village. Rama might have rested under this pipal tree."⁴

Kenchamma holds a legendary status within the Puranic tradition in the novel. The past interweaves with the present, and the deities engage with humanity. Kanthapurians are ardent devotees of Kenchamma and engage in hymns to appease Kenchamma, the gracious and generous Goddess, the embodiment of life, harvest queen crowned with rain. Kenchamma, the benevolent and magnanimous Goddess, is the indigenous deity who perpetually protects. The experiences of famine, disease, death, and despair are profoundly embedded in the consciousness of the Kanthapurians, prompting them to present their first rice or fruit in reverence, along with offerings of 'saris' and bodice-cloth for every birth and marriage (pp. 9-10). The populace believes that Kenchamma actively interacts with them in times of adversity, granting blessings and safeguarding them from dangers and afflictions. She saves them from smallpox and cholera. In times of drought, Kenchamma helps her devotees by granting rain, and "She smiles upon you a smile such as you have never before beheld"⁵ (9). She unwaveringly aids her followers in their grief; however, her sphere of benevolence is confined to Kanthapura. As a result, she cannot help people who are residing in the neighboring village Talassana. The episode in which Kenchamma confronts the demon who kills the young man of the village and violates their wives bears resemblance to the Durga Purana, where Goddess Durga slays the demon Mahishasura. It gives the local legend a mythical quality, turning Kenchamma into a figure of divine resistance against evil. Achakka claims that Kenchamma fights the forces of darkness over and over again until they are defeated so violently that their blood is thought to have seeped into the ground and turned the soil of Kenchamma Hill permanently red. This kind of mythologizing helps the people to see Kenchamma's struggle as a metaphor for their own resistance against British rule.

The Goddess is shown to control the whole cycle of human activity and is connected to river Himavathi, which has a local symbolism for the villagers. The villagers get strength from this belief, as Range Gowda says, "I drank three handfuls of Himavathy water and I said, "protect us, Mother"⁶ (258). Their sense of faith is further reinforced by the idea that the goddess of the river converses all night with the goddess of the hill, embodying the inherent feminine power present in both land and water.

The novel vividly describes the mythical grandeur of the river Himavathy. The river is portrayed as a living deity, able to affect the villagers' fate with the power of Puranic gods and goddesses. An example of this mythic imagination is the description of the river's solemn role in the last rites of the pious Ramakrishna. Flowing with silent dignity, the river lets the rituals happen, only to erupt in anger and carry away all traces of the cremation, carrying the idea in the form of ashes and bone (146). In this way, the river becomes both a witness and a participant in the sacred drama of human life, reinforcing its status as a powerful mythological presence in the story.

Henry Whitehead observes the influence of the local deity on individuals, asserting, "Shiva and Vishnu may be more dignified beings, but the village deity is regarded as a more present help in trouble and is more intimately concerned with the happiness and prosperity of the villagers."⁷ (quoted by Naik 66) The tale of Goddess Kenchamma's invocation in Kanthapura has a mythical parallel in the Ganga-Purana. Similar to the sacred river Ganga's descent from Vaikuntha to sanctify the mortal remains of his cursed ancestors, Kenchamma descends from the heavens to assist the denizens of Kanthapura. Gandhi's impact on Indian villages is depicted as profoundly religious and spiritual, rather than merely political. The transformation of villagers is brought up by Moorthy, who is disciple of Gandhi and emerges as a miniature Gandhi and evolves into a center force in the life of villagers. Gandhiji's influence is all pervasive, but he remains invisible like Godot but remains throughout a potent force in villagers' consciousness and Moorthy's actions.

The villagers endeavor to purify not only their own personal shortcomings but also the sins of the community through prayer and penance, thereby transforming suffering into a moral force. Gita's doctrine of selfless action is embodied in actions and philosophy of satyagrah as lived by Moorthy. Moorthy assumes larger than life proportions because of his ascetic discipline and devotion. He takes upon himself sufferings of others as saints do and his life becomes resonant with spiritual sacrifice and moral authority. The villagers motivated by his example, spontaneously unite under his leadership and resist colonial authority. Pain is portrayed as transformative and redemptive force. Suffering is given a sacred dimension and becomes a means of self purification. It draws on Gandhian concept of self imposed penance as a method of absorbing collective wrongs. Fasting as

a means of mental and spiritual discipline aims to purify and counteract violence and injustice.

Gandhi's non violent resistance against British rule finds parallel in allegorical representation wherein Gandhi is Rama, Jawahar Lal Nehru is Bharata. Gandhi's visit to England to attend Round Table Conference in 1931 is likened to Rama's visit to Lanka to bring Sita back. The narrative technique used by Jayaramchar in his Harikatha to narrate Gandhi's life is in manner of epic storytelling, combining historical events with puranic imagery. His birth and mission are described in religious terms, as if they were preordained by Gods for victory of righteous and downfall of evil.

Raja Rao places Gandhiji in line of avatars by drawing comparison to Rama and Krishna. The fusion of myth and history makes the novel move from political narrative to religious one. Gandhi himself is transformed into invisible divinity, while Moorthy becomes his visible deputy. The narrative is deeply rooted in plethora of festivals celebrated with zest, devotion and fervor such as Sankara jayanti, Rama navmi and Krishna Jayanti. During kartik season, gods are envisioned as traversing the streets and their divine presence is invoked to dispel the darkness.

Conclusion

Raja Rao establishes a mythical framework that seamlessly integrates myth and reality, transforming political conflict into cosmic drama of good versus evil. The force of evil embodied in the form of exploitation rampant in Skeffington Coffee Estate becomes a miniature battlefield of this mythical conflict. Raja Rao elevates the freedom struggle from a political episode to an eternal struggle between truth and falsehood, righteousness and tyranny by incorporating myth, legends and rituals into the narrative's fabric. Thus *Kanthapura* becomes not a narrative of a single village but a symbolic *Purana* of India's nationalist awakening.

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